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“HUMAN RIGHTS LOOMS!”

North, South, East, and West,
deepest beats of heart that loom and bloom as one.
Humanity's freedom must prevail and unveil;
ethnicity, diversity, and grace being thee—
equality and equity, as said to be.

From the grassroots and hinterland
to the urban city streets and rural fertile grounds,
each persona resounds respect,
social integration and the mainstream.
Dignity and freedom, expressions more on thee—
a universal language of truth for you and me.

No matter the color, creed, political or economic status, and race,
human rights must find their innermost recesses and never lose.

Freedom of expression, knitted to coat,
empowering souls—unwavering, never lost.

Education, shelter, healthcare—a life full and whole,
for in every right, basic and profound.

For every ethnicity, a soul, a spirit resounds
that deserves to thrive with unwavering strides,
defending human rights so that all that is right becomes might.

In every human ethnicity and soul,
a word of equality and equity foretold—
will never fade, but rise and empower
every soul to stand and hold.